

FATIGUE FAILURE MECHANISM OF CONTINUOUS FIBER UNIDIRECTIONALLY REINFORCED INTERMETALLIC COMPOUND MATRIX COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this paper is to characterize the fatigue damage tolerance behavior of unidirectionally continuous fiber reinforced intermetallic compound matrix composites. The fatigue crack growth tests were conducted in a room temperature on continuous silicon carbide fiber unidirectionally reinforced intermetallic titanium aluminide compound matrix composite $\text{SiC}_{\text{CVD}}/\text{Ti}_3\text{Al+Nb}$ using single edge notched (SEN) specimens. The fatigue failure mechanisms were investigated on the basis of fracture mechanics and electron fractography. The analysis of stress intensity factor at the fatigue crack tip with the reinforcement fiber bridging were also done in order to evaluate the fatigue crack growth resistance. It is found that there is essentially little difference of the fatigue crack growth resistance between $\text{SiC}_{\text{CVD}}/\text{Ti}_3\text{Al+Nb}$ and matrix intermetallic $\text{Ti}_3\text{Al+Nb}$ compound.

Keywords: Fracture Mechanics, Intermetallic Compound Matrix Composite, Fatigue Failure Mechanism, Fatigue Crack Growth Resistance, Fiber Pressure Model

1. INTRODUCTION

Various advanced structural materials have recently been researched and developed in the field of aeronautics and aerospace technologies [1]. Intermetallic compound matrix composites (IMCs) are one of these materials, and are generally considered to be attractive as structural materials for high temperature application. It is the most important and urgent problems to characterize the damage tolerance behavior for a wide use of advanced IMCs for primary aeronautics and aerospace structural applications.

The purpose of this paper is to characterize the fatigue damage tolerance behavior of unidirectionally continuous fiber reinforced intermetallic compound matrix composites. The fatigue crack growth tests were conducted in a room temperature on continuous silicon carbide fiber unidirectionally reinforced intermetallic titanium aluminide compound matrix composite $\text{SiC}_{\text{CVD}}/\text{Ti}_3\text{Al+Nb}$ using single edge notched (SEN) specimens. The analysis of stress intensity factor at the fatigue crack tip based on fiber pressure model [2] were also done in order to evaluate the effect of reinforcement fiber bridging on the fatigue crack growth behavior. The fatigue crack growth characteristics were investigated on the basis of fracture mechanics and electron microfractography in comparison with that for metal matrix composites (MMCs) [3-7], especially β -type titanium alloy matrix composite [8].

2. FCG CHARACTERISTICS OF MMCs

A summary of the observed macroscopic fatigue crack growth (FCG) behavior in the unidirectionally continuous fiber SiC_{CVD} reinforced aluminum and titanium alloys matrix composites is schematically

Figure 1. A schematic illustration of fatigue crack growth behavior in unidirectional continuous fiber reinforced metal matrix composites.

illustrated in Figure 1 [7]. Fatigue crack growth behavior is found to be dependent upon the matrix metal and the fiber/matrix interface characteristics. One great difference is that the longitudinal fatigue crack growth did not occur in the case of Al alloy matrix composite, while in the case of Ti alloy matrix composite both the longitudinal and the mixed-mode (Modes I and II) FCG behavior occurred with a breaking the reinforcement fibers. A weak interface and greatly different mechanical properties between the reinforcement fiber and the matrix led to interfacial debonding within the plastic zone at the crack tip in the case of SiC_{CVD}/Al alloys, and caused the crack to propagate the fiber/matrix interface. A strong interface and relatively minor difference in mechanical properties allowed little debonding and crack propagated with the fiber breakage in SiC_{CVD}/Ti alloys.

3. MATERIAL AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

3.1. Material

The material chosen for this investigation is a unidirectional four-ply SiC_{CVD}/Ti₃Al+Nb composite. The reinforcing phase (approximately 35 volume-percent) was continuous 140 mm diameter SiC fibers, commercially designated as SCS-6. The matrix material was a α_2 -phase Ti₃Al+Nb intermetallic compound. The composite was fabricated by hot isostatically pressing (HIP-ing) alternate layers of fibers and thin foils of Ti₃Al+Nb. Figure 2 shows cross section through the thickness of the composite showing the four layers of fibers covered at the outer surface by three thin matrix films. The material is well consolidated between fibers, and fiber spacing is somewhat irregular. The average room temperature mechanical properties of the composite are also listed in Table 1. It is highly anisotropic properties, whose tensile strength and elastic modulus value is much greater parallel to the fiber direction (L) than in the transverse direction (T).

Table 1. Mechanical properties.

Material	Ori.	E GPa	σ_{UTS} MPa	ϵ_f %
SiC _{CVD} /Ti ₃ Al+Nb	L	175	1150	1.05

Figure 2. Cross section of composite in as-fabricated condition.

3.2. Test Procedure

The specimens used are single edge notched (SEN) specimen with the tensile axis oriented along the reinforcement fiber direction (0 degree IMCs) as shown in Figure 3. A initial single edge notch of approximately 5 mm long with 0.2 mm width was electrodischarged in each specimen. The surfaces of the notches were subsequently polished using emery paper.

Figure 3. Configuration and dimensions of test specimen.

The fatigue crack growth tests were conducted in a room temperature environment at a constant load amplitude with a constant stress ratio R of 0.05 and 0.5 using a MTS closed-loop electrohydraulic materials testing system according to ASTM E647 Standards. The increments of crack extension were directly measured using a traveling microscope. After the tests, fractographic examinations were performed on the cross section and surface of specimen using a scanning electron microscope.

4. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

4.1. Fatigue Crack Growth Curve

Figure 4 shows the fatigue crack growth curves measured at $R=0.05$ and 0.5 , respectively. The crack growth rates da/dN decrease with an increase in the crack length followed by an eventual crack arrest. It is almost similar to the FCG behaviors for $\text{SiC}_{\text{CVD}}/\text{Ti-15V-3Cr-3Al-3Sn}$ (Ti-15-3) reported in the previous paper [8].

From the optical micrographs of crack plane in the layers shown in Figure 5, it is found that the reinforcement fibers are not broken resulting in fiber bridging of the crack wake. It is not a stress-free in the crack plane. That is to say, the reinforcement fibers are loaded partially in the crack plane, and results in a decrease of stress intensity at the fatigue crack tip. It is considered to be mainly due to the crack arrest in FCG behavior at a constant load amplitude.

Figure 4. Fatigue crack growth curves.

Crack propagation direction \rightarrow

Figure 5. Crack growth behavior resulting in fiber bridging of the crack wake.

4.2. Relationship between da/dN and ΔK_{app}

Figure 6 shows the relationship between da/dN and apparent stress intensity factor range ΔK_{app} . The ΔK_{app} was calculated by considering only applied load amplitude and the crack length without taking into consideration the reinforcement fiber bridging of the cracked surfaces. It is found from this figure that the da/dN data are uniquely related to ΔK_{app} , and that da/dN at every stress ratios decreases with an increase of ΔK_{app} until an eventual crack arrest was achieved. And da/dN at $R=0.05$ are larger than that at $R=0.5$ at the same ΔK level. It is quite different from the da/dN - ΔK relationship for the ordinary metallic materials.

Figure 6. Fatigue crack growth rates as a function of apparent stress intensity factor range ΔK_{app} .

Figure 8. Relationships between da/dN and ΔK_{tip} for SiC_{CVD} / Ti_3Al+Nb .

on the threshold stress intensity factor range ΔK_{th} determined at $da/dN=10^{-10}$ m/cycle and the ΔK_{th} are approximately 10.0 (R=0.05) and 2.5 $MPa\sqrt{m}$ (R=0.5) respectively. It can also be seen from this figure that the $da/dN-\Delta K_{tip}$ relationship for SiC_{CVD} / Ti_3Al+Nb is fairly corresponded with the $da/dN-\Delta K$ relationship for the matrix intermetallic Ti_3Al+Nb compound. Generally, the high residual stress is induced from the mismatch of the thermal expansion between the fiber and the matrix during the fabricating process of IMCs [10]. The residual stress play a role in the fatigue crack growth behavior. It is necessary for the further research to evaluate quantitatively the effect of residual stress on the fatigue crack growth characteristics of IMCs.

5.3. Comparison of fatigue crack resistance with $SiC_{CVD} / Ti-15-3$

The $da/dN-\Delta K_{tip}$ relationship obtained at R=0.05 is also shown by the solid line in Figure 8 for $SiC_{CVD} / Ti-15-3$. It can also be seen from this figure that the da/dN for SiC_{CVD} / Ti_3Al+Nb are one or two orders lower than that for $SiC_{CVD} / Ti-15-3$ at same ΔK_{tip} level. In summary, the fatigue crack growth resistance near threshold for SiC_{CVD} / Ti_3Al+Nb is superior to $SiC_{CVD} / Ti-15-3$. It is considered to be due to the difference of the reinforcement fiber bridging resulted from the fiber/matrix interface characteristics.

6. CONCLUSION

The fatigue crack growth tests were conducted on continuous fiber unidirectionally reinforced intermetallic titanium aluminide compound matrix composite SiC_{CVD} / Ti_3Al+Nb . The fatigue crack growth resistance was evaluated on the basis of the analytical results of stress intensity factor with considering the fiber bridging effect. The conclusions may be summarized as follows;

- (1) There is a remarkable influence of the reinforcement fiber bridging on the fatigue crack growth behavior. The fatigue crack growth rates da/dN decrease with increasing crack length and the crack growth is eventually arrested.

- (2) The da/dN decreases with an increase of the apparent stress intensity factor range ΔK_{app} , although the da/dN are uniquely related to ΔK_{app} . It is quite different from the ordinary metallic materials.
- (3) The stress intensity factor range ΔK_{tip} at a fatigue crack tip with the reinforcement fiber bridging are successfully analyzed based on fiber pressure model.
- (4) The da/dN increases with increasing the ΔK_{tip} at every stress ratio. There is also a remarkable influence of stress ratio on the da/dN - ΔK_{tip} relationship, and the da/dN at same ΔK_{tip} level increases with increasing the stress ratio.
- (5) The da/dN - ΔK_{tip} relationship for SiC_{CVD}/Ti_3Al+Nb is fairly good agreement with da/dN - ΔK relationship for the matrix intermetallic Ti_3Al+Nb compound. There is essentially little difference of the fatigue crack growth resistance between SiC_{CVD}/Ti_3Al+Nb and the matrix intermetallic Ti_3Al+Nb compound.
- (6) The fatigue crack growth resistance near threshold for SiC_{CVD}/Ti_3Al+Nb is superior to $SiC_{CVD}/Ti-15-3$.

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